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International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/ijdr

Earthquake early warning in countries where damaging earthquakes only occur every 50 to 150 years – The societal perspective

Irina Dallo^{a,b,*}, Michèle Marti^a, John Clinton^a, Maren Böse^a, Frédérick Massin^a, Simone Zaugg^a

^a Swiss Seismological Service at ETH Zurich, Switzerland

^b Transdisciplinarity Lab, ETH Zurich, Switzerland

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Earthquake early warning
Public reaction
Message design
System preferences
Information recall

ABSTRACT

Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) systems can trigger actions just before the shaking hits and hence mitigate the impact of damaging earthquakes. Recent studies have mainly focused on technical challenges, performance or on the attitudes of the public towards EEW systems in countries where EEW systems are already in operation or where damaging earthquakes are frequent. Building on these efforts, from the societal perspective we assess how different message elements influence the intention to take action and ability to grasp relevant information within a few seconds. Further, we explore the public attitudes towards EEW systems in a country where damaging earthquakes are expected less frequently. In a survey (N = 596, between-subjects experiment) targeting the Swiss public, we assess EEW system preferences and test different versions of EEW messages to identify elements which trigger people to take immediate actions and can be correctly recalled. Our main findings are that i) the public attitudes in countries with moderate seismic hazard are similar to attitudes in countries with high seismic hazard; ii) pictograms trigger people to protect themselves on the spot whereas maps prompt the public to look for further information or to warn others; iii) the designs preferred by the public are not always those that actually trigger them to take action; and iv) people tend to react proportionally to the hazard level. We show that insights from studies focusing on societal issues related to EEW systems can help operators define technical settings and to address specific concerns or likely misconceptions in education campaigns.

1. Introduction

Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) systems have the ability to provide warnings just before the shaking hits and thereby allow protective action to be taken, increasing societal resilience to earthquakes. In 2020, EEW systems were operational in nine countries and being tested in thirteen others [1].

The primary aims of EEW systems are to notify the public about imminent strong ground shaking, enabling people to protect themselves, and to trigger automated shutdowns or safety procedures such as slowing down trains, returning elevators to the ground floor, or securing critical infrastructure [2–4]. Furthermore, EEW systems support individuals and institutions who want rapid

* Corresponding author. ETH Zurich, Swiss Seismological Service, Sonneggstrasse 5, 8092, Zurich, Switzerland.

E-mail address: irina.dallo@sed.ethz.ch (I. Dallo).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2022.103441>

Received 13 September 2022; Received in revised form 9 November 2022; Accepted 9 November 2022

Available online 11 November 2022

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earthquake information for situational awareness purposes [2] and rescue operations [5].

However, technical challenges limit the effectiveness of EEW systems. The strongest motion and hence damage from earthquakes is typically centred around the epicentral region, with the impacted area generally increasing with earthquake size. No warnings can be issued in advance of shaking to those located directly at the epicentre (blind zone) which only receive a warning at the same time or shortly after the shaking hits [6–8]. Just beyond this region, the warning times are short, growing in size with distance from the epicentre. Hence it is challenging to provide effective, concise and actionable advice about the actions to take [8–10]. Further, false alerts or missed events are always possible [10]. In particular for low magnitude earthquakes the probability of false alerts is quite high. However, the greater the magnitude and therefore the potential of economic and human losses, the better the system may work [11]. Additionally, for low hazard regions, the cost-benefit ratio of implementing an EEW system may be negative [8], though in more seismically hazardous regions the benefits outweigh the costs [4]. However, in high hazard regions it should also be evaluated whether it is preferable to invest in an EEW system or other measures [12].

Moreover, EEW systems face further challenges from a societal perspective (see section 2). For example, what alert thresholds and which communication channel does the public prefer? Does the public know which actions they can/should take to protect themselves? Does the message design influence people's intention to take action? Nakayachi et al. [13] conducted a survey analysing public's reactions to EEW alerts and their general preferences in Japan. Becker et al. [14] conducted a similar survey assessing New Zealanders' attitudes towards EEW systems as a basis for the implementation of an EEW system, analysing also the effects of previous earthquake experiences [15]. The available studies addressing such societal issues have mainly focused on countries where EEW systems are already operational [9,13] or where damaging earthquakes occur regularly [14]. However, there are many countries where damaging earthquakes are less frequent and consequently the public's awareness and preparedness levels are lower than in the countries where strong earthquakes occur more often. Despite being less frequent, strong or catastrophic events still have to be expected in countries with moderate earthquake hazard. Therefore, it is important to assess the potential of EEW systems also in these countries [16], to assess their potential from a societal perspective, and compare it with that of other countries.

Our case study was conducted in Switzerland, a country with moderate hazard levels and where a damaging earthquake is expected every 50–150 years. Switzerland further is a rich country with strong adherence to a good building code, so public confidence in the built environment and their own safety is high. In our study, we conducted an online survey with two between-subject experiments (=each participant is exposed to only one treatment) in order to assess the Swiss public's EEW system preferences and to test different EEW message versions [17]. The survey results allow us to compare the Swiss public attitudes towards EEW systems with preferences in other countries [13,14], and to test which EEW message elements trigger what kind of actions and are perceived to be the most useful, which has not been done before. Our study thus provides empirical results of practical use not only for researchers but also disaster managers and communicators in charge of designing user-centred EEW alerts.

2. The societal perspective of EEW systems

In this section, we highlight the relevant societal aspects related to EEW systems, namely the history of public alerts, the dissemination channels, the thought process about setting meaningful thresholds, the importance of actionable message content, the technical limitations and preferences with respect to warning times, people's reactions when receiving warnings, and the need of post-alert messages. Overall, public perception of the usefulness of EEW alerts is known to be high in the US [18], Mexico [19], Japan [13], Peru [20], and New Zealand [14].

2.1. Public alerts

In August 1993, the first EEW alerts were provided to the public in Mexico City. Today, Japan, Korea, Taiwan, and the US are sending alerts to the public too [2]. Romania and Turkey send alerts to selected users, meanwhile Italy, Switzerland, China, Israel, Chile, Guatemala, Costa Rica, El Salvador, and Nicaragua are still in the technical testing phase [2,12]. Further, the Earthquake Network (EQN) initiative provides EEW alerts via their smartphone app in multiple countries [20,21]. And since 2021, Google has been rolling out smartphone-based alerts via Android cell-phones to countries across the world [22].

In the earliest stages, real-time warnings were distributed through public AM and FM radio stations, sirens, and TV channels [23]. Today, EEW alerts are delivered in a user-friendly and customizable way through mobile applications (apps), cell broadcasting, and machine-to-machine processes [24–26]. Often EEW alerts are also distributed via numerous different channels to enhance their effectiveness. In Japan, for example, they are shared via J-ALERT (wireless radio system), Cell Broadcast Services (CBS), and an earthquake app. Japan further installed satellite-linked telecommunications equipment as a backup to terrestrial communications [10]. In the US, apps, i.e. QuakeAlert USA and MyShake, and WEA alerts are used to disseminate EEW alerts to the public since 2019. In Taiwan, earthquake announcements are distributed via the weather app run by the Meteorological Office (i.e., Weather department) [27]. The benefit of disseminating alerts via weather apps is that a large part of the society is already using them [28]. App-based systems are preferred, as Becker et al. [14] showed for New Zealand, where people wish to receive warnings via their mobile phones supported by other channels. Such a preference has also been observed in Mexico [29]. Apps support collection of user feedback, though they suffer from the possibility of being turned off or misconfigured by the user.

2.2. Alert threshold

On the July 4, 2019, a strong M7.1 earthquake occurred in the Southern California (US) Ridgecrest area which was a first serious test for the United States West Coast ShakeAlert system [30]. In addition to magnitude underestimation [31], the system did not work as expected from the user perspective. The developers assumed that people do not want to be notified when the ground shaking was

perceptible but not damaging, which was not the case [32]. Therefore, the ground motion thresholds were lowered after this event [33]. This is in line with Bossu et al. [34] who concluded that the public demands real-time information for all earthquakes that are felt. In Japan, a warning is only issued to the general public when the maximum seismic intensity is expected to be VII–VIII or above on the MMI scale [35]. In Taiwan, in comparison, they set the threshold slightly higher to a magnitude of 4.5 [27], corresponding to near-source intensities of about V–VI. In New Zealand, people hypothetically wished to receive earthquake warnings beginning from MMI V–VI [36]. Summing up, the alert thresholds vary regionally and, consequently, have to be defined for each country separately. To this end, it is important that scientists, engineers and technicians align their expectations with those of the public or other end users [37].

2.3. Message content and design

EEW messages should prioritize providing actionable information [38,39]. In particular, users wish to be informed about the expected time until the shaking starts, how strong the shaking might be, and what to do during the shaking [2]. At best, the recommendation behavior should be available and presented in such a way that they account for different situations, e.g. being at home or in a car [39]. However, it is not trivial to define the most appropriate recommendation because this depends on multiple factors such as the social, cultural, and environmental context, demographic characteristics or the magnitude/intensity of an earthquake [9].

The alert design is important too. Studies have shown that pictograms increase public's motivation, comprehension, and compliance to warning information [40] and, in turn, speed-up and improve cognitive processing [41]. Maps may also increase the willingness to take action because people in the hazard zone feel personally affected when receiving a warning with a map [42]. The map should include the event location, relevant regional borders and key cities so it can be rapidly digested by users [43]. Further, credibility is enhanced if a trustful source is indicated in the alert [44]. Moreover, a prominent warning text such as "strong shaking expected" should be highlighted and supplemented with additional information about the earthquake and secondary hazards such as tsunamis [36]. Also for the behavioral recommendations short and clear textual indications are wished [42]. Further, the alerts should be informative enough to reduce milling, thus looking for further information [45]. To this end, it is particularly important to avoid ambiguous information [44] and the use of jargon [45]. In addition, interactive features can be added at the bottom of the message to allow receivers to respond effectively after the shaking is over, e.g. report or help button, sharing function [46,47]. If all these aspects are considered, the public can better understand the information provided and, consequently, have increased compliance with the preferred actions [48].

2.4. Triggered actions and available time to respond

Nakayachi et al. [13] showed that people in Japan tend to react mostly mentally and less physically and, therefore, remained calm when receiving a warning. The same also applies to people in the US [49], Peru [26] and Mexico [50]. This can be explained as i) people only expect low intensity ground motion and consequently decide that there is no need to do anything; ii) they think that they are safe at their current location; and iii) they do not know what they should and have to do [13]. Additionally, by not knowing the time available to respond, people expressed a concern that they just would stand still and prepare mentally instead of taking protective actions [14]. However, another study showed that people in Japan reported that they took physical protective actions in a nursery, kindergarten, school, at home, and at work [51]. People tend to respond more actively especially when an earthquake generates strong shaking or when their fear level is high [18]. In addition to mentally preparing themselves for the shaking or taking protective actions, many people also tend to look for further information to verify the warning [13,52], warn their relatives [20,26], or interact to build a joint understanding of what will (is) happen(ing) [13,46]. However, people do not have enough time to do these actions first before protecting themselves on the spot.

On average, people have only a few seconds when receiving an EEW alert to take protective actions. Is that enough? Emolo et al. [53] showed that 3–5 s are sufficient for well-trained students in Campania to protect themselves before the shaking starts (e.g., go under a table). In New Zealand, people said that 5–10 s would be enough for them to easily take protective actions (e.g., stop the car, go under a table, mentally prepare). Longer times would even allow them to move to a safe area (e.g., garden), help others, or look for more information [36]. However, one must ensure that people know that the warning time is highly variable and not fixed or constant to avoid any misconceptions [54].

2.5. False alerts

Most users in the US perceive EEW alerts as useful and tolerate false alerts as they offer practical training opportunities [2]; however, post-alert update messages with context and explanations are expected [18]. In Japan, users also expressed a positive attitude towards false alerts after the Tohoku earthquake, arguing that they represented an opportunity to practice protective actions [55]. Similar levels of tolerance by the public have also been observed in Peru [20,26]. When people in Mexico City were asked what they considered a false alert, they described an alert that was not triggered by an earthquake, they did not refer to an alert issued for a real earthquake that did not cause felt shaking at their location [29]. This implies that users have a higher tolerance for unnecessary alerts than for missed alerts [2]. However, other studies concluded that receiving too many alerts and especially false alerts, negatively affects the credibility of an EEW system [56,57]. Pescaroli et al. [54] also showed that in particular mature EEW receivers (e.g., local organisations including civil protection and education institutions) perceive false alerts as disturbing rather than useful.

2.6. Subsequent messages

Many injuries and deaths also occur in the hours, days, or weeks following the main shock due to secondary hazards such as landslides (e.g., Wenchuan 2008), tsunamis (e.g., Haiti 2010), or damages on critical infrastructure (e.g., Fukushima 2011). In New Zealand and the US, people thus would like to receive a follow-up message including information about the probability of secondary hazards such as tsunamis [36,58]. Further information after the EEW message could be a detailed map of the affected areas, information about aftershocks, and a list of emergency numbers [46]. Moreover, a subsequent message may also counteract mistrust in the system after false and missed alerts, which is already done in Mexico. Thus, EEW alerts should be paired with robust messaging before, during, and after an earthquake [59].

2.7. Effectiveness of the system

The comprehension, credibility, and personalization of the warning are relevant factors of the decision-taking process and, thus, impact the effectiveness of EEW [52]. Trust in the sender of the message is decisive, too, and influences whether receivers will take action or not [60]. The effectiveness also depends on personal resources such as self-efficacy, response efficacy, and practical skills [13].

There are several strategies that support increasing the effectiveness of an EEW system. First, information campaigns and training are important to support an adequate response to an EEW alert. Sutton et al. [52], for example, showed that people who were exposed to an instructional video had a higher reported understanding of the EEW system and a higher ability to take an immediate decision about what to do. In Japan, an awareness campaign was launched and brochures as well as videos distributed to highlight in form of various scenarios how to best prepare and react when receiving an EEW alert [10]. These efforts help transform declarative knowledge to procedural knowledge [39,52]. Second, in order to reduce public's mistrust in the system and improve their understanding of the capabilities and limitations of EEW systems [19], the technical limitations should be transparently communicated [35,61]. Third, Becker et al. [36] emphasizes that countries with already mature systems must be prepared to address normalization biases. Fourth, drills allow people and organisations to practice protective actions, whereby not the quantity but the quality matters (e.g., identifying specific training deficits) [54]. Fifth, inclusivity increases the effectiveness of EEW systems, which is why Jenkins et al. [62] developed self-reflective questions that help institutions in charge to develop inclusive communication practices, addressing especially vulnerable people in society. Sixth, to make sure that the system is tailored to the end user needs, the involvement of all relevant stakeholders, i.e. civil protection, emergency services, and decision makers must be ensured during the development, implementation, and operational phase [8,54,61,63].

2.8. Research gaps and questions

Velazquez et al. [64] highlight two research gaps regarding EEW alerts from a societal perspective. First, EEW systems lack the integration of multi-disciplinary perspectives, leading to limited effectiveness and applications for end users. Second, a precise evaluation of the information that should be included in the EEW messages is required in order to trigger useful mitigation action. Nakayachi et al. [13] and Sutton et al. [52] also stressed the latter research gap when they state the need to better explore what information elements are most important when the alert time is short, and how should the information best be presented. Further, Auclair et al. [16] highlight a research gap with regards to the exploration of public attitudes towards and expectations of EEW systems in countries with moderate seismic hazard levels; only professional stakeholders have been involved in such countries so far. For our Swiss case study, we thus focused on the following two research questions:

- (1) Which attributes of an EEW system (i.e., intensity threshold, minimum warning time for an adequate response, warning channel, warning content) does the public prefer in moderate seismic hazard countries?
- (2) Do different elements of an EEW message have an impact on how a warning is perceived and on the actions triggered?

3. Method

3.1. Procedure and sample

We conducted an online survey with two between-subject experiments (= each participant is exposed to only one treatment) in Switzerland's German- and French-speaking regions in March 2021. The survey was programmed in Unipark and pre-tested in order to improve the clarity of the questions and the technical functionalities. We did a statistical power analysis using G*Power to calculate the required number of participants, which led us to 600 participants [65,66]. The participants were recruited through the ISO-accredited polling company Respondi. We used quota sampling with quotas based on language, age, and gender representing the population of Switzerland. In total, 960 people were recruited with an answer rate of 63.39%. Due to short answer durations and the failure of the quality check, we had to exclude 30 participants [67]. The survey was approved by the Ethics Committee of ETH Zurich (EK 2020-N-46).

The final 596 participants ranged in age from 18 to 80 years ($M = 43.73$, $SD = 14.87$). 49.3% were female and 50.7% male. Further, 26.0% spoke French and 74.0% German. Most participants worked full-time (49.8%) or part time (16.3%). The other characteristics of the participants are listed in the Supplements S1a-d. The sample characteristics – age, gender, education, living place, work position, persons with disabilities, earthquake insurance, house property and income – did not significantly differ across the ten EEW message versions (Supplements S2a&b).

3.2. Survey design

The survey consisted of five question blocks (QB) as summarized in [Appendix B](#). In QB1, we assessed participants' earthquake experience, exposure and preparedness levels as well as their knowledge about EEW systems. In QB2, the participants were provided with a description of a hypothetical visit to friends in a Swiss city where they received an EEW alert. They were then provided with one of the ten EEW message versions. We stressed that they would see the message only for a few seconds, in an attempt to mimic a stressful situation similar to when they would receive an EEW message. Participants saw or heard the message for either 3 s or five 5 s. Afterwards, they had to indicate which actions they would take and which information they recall. In addition, they were asked whether the time was sufficient to grasp all relevant information. In QB3, the participants had the chance to see or hear the EEW message again and were requested to rate whether the message was informative, clear, trustworthy, understandable, and useful. In addition, we asked general questions about certain attributes of EEW systems (alert threshold, warning time wished to adequately respond, technical limitations, general concerns, preferred channels). Finally, we assessed the participants' sociodemographic characteristics. Where reasonable, we used a 5-point Likert scale and randomized the answers. A complete list of questions is given in the Supplements S3-c (German, French and English version available). The questions in QB1, QB3 and QB5 were adopted from the EEW survey conducted in New Zealand and Japan [14] and adapted to fit the Swiss context. In QB2, we used between-subject experiments to test the different message versions by randomly assigning participants to one of ten EEW message versions (English versions in: [Table 1](#) & [Table 2](#); German & French versions in [Supplement S4](#)). The EEW messages were designed based on insights from 65 interviews conducted with the public in Switzerland, Italy, Iceland in the summer 2020, best practices from other countries, and feedback from seismologists. In QB4, we further tested rapid earthquake information messages, which are not addressed in this article.

3.3. Analysis

We used [SPSS](#) for the frequency analyses and the significance tests of the quantitative data. Several one-way analyses of variances (ANOVAs) were conducted to determine the effect of the message design and participants' earthquake experience on their preferences, interpretation abilities, and perceived usefulness of the EEW messages. We used Bonferroni post-hoc tests to compare pairwise whether these differences were significant. Additionally, to analyse the effect of the message design on participants' intended first actions, we used binomial logistic regressions and multinomial logistic regressions. Multinomial logistic regressions were used when there were multiple categorical outcomes of interest [68]. The free-response answers were categorized with the software NVivo [69], following an inductive research procedure [70].

4. Results

4.1. Earthquake experience, preparedness and exposure

First the participants were asked whether they have ever experienced an earthquake, whether they have taken any preparedness actions so far, and how they evaluate their exposure to earthquakes (Supplements S5a-c).

63.1% of the participants had already *felt an earthquake*. However, only 1.9% had personally experienced injury, damage, or loss from earthquakes. Furthermore, participants came across information about damaging earthquakes on media (71.5%) and in movies (64.3%). Further 37.1% of the participants also learnt about the possible impacts of earthquakes at school. The majority of the participants who had already felt an earthquake, felt only light (44.7%) or very light shaking (33.4%). Only 15.5% and 6.3% felt moderate or strong to very strong shaking, respectively. Regarding their reactions during or after the shaking, most participants stated that they stopped what they were doing and stayed still (45.8%), talked about the event with friends, family or neighbours (38.4%), looked for information on the internet (24.8%), woke up (23.2%) or woke up but fell immediately asleep again (18.3%). Only a handful of them went under a table/doorframe (6.0%) or ran outside the building (6.0%). Additionally, most of them were not worried at all during or after the shaking ($M = 3.19$, $SD = 1.38$), they rather found it exciting ($M = 2.85$, $SD = 1.32$).

Based on the behavioral recommendations defined by the Swiss Seismological Service (SED) at ETH Zurich and the Federal Office for Civil Protection (FOCP), we put together a list with *preparedness measures* for earthquakes and disasters in general. Overall, 57.9% of all participants have taken at least one preparedness measure and 42.1% have taken none. On average, participants took one measure ($M = 1.06$, $SD = 1.19$), mostly they looked for information on how to respond to strong shaking due to an earthquake (66.6%) and on how to prepare for an emergency such as earthquakes (40.3%). Some participants had further prepared an emergency kit

Table 1
EEW message versions with their attributes.

EEW message versions	Format [visual or audio]	Content [map or pictograms]	Shaking intensity [weak or strong]	Display [3 or 5 s]
Version 1 [wm3]	visual	map	weak	3 s
Version 2 [wm5]	visual	map	weak	5 s
Version 3 [sm3]	visual	map	strong	3 s
Version 4 [sm5]	visual	map	strong	5 s
Version 5 [wp3]	visual	pictograms	weak	3 s
Version 6 [wp5]	visual	pictograms	weak	5 s
Version 7 [sp3]	visual	pictograms	strong	3 s
Version 8 [sp5]	visual	pictograms	strong	5 s
Version 9 [aw]	audio	-	weak	-
Version 10 [as]	audio	-	strong	-

Table 2
EEW message versions. The German and French versions are listed in [Supplement S4](#).

Versions 1 & 2	Versions 3 & 4	Versions 5 & 6
<p>Weak shaking message with a map [wm]</p>		
<p>Versions 7 & 8 Strong shaking message with pictograms [sp]</p>	<p>Version 9 Audio weak shaking message [aw]</p> <p>“Attention earthquake! Weak shaking possible at your location! Be prepared.”</p>	<p>Version 10 Audio strong shaking message [as]</p> <p>“Attention earthquake! Take cover. Strong shaking possible at your location.”</p>

(19.7%) or practiced in an earthquake drill (15.4%).

Regarding *earthquake exposure*, the participants tend to agree that a strong earthquake in Switzerland would affect the quality of their life ($M = 3.41, SD = 1.11$). In addition, they supported the statement that an earthquake is possible in Switzerland with a higher extent compared to the one that a damaging earthquake in Switzerland is probable ($t(595) = 13.81, p < .001$). On the contrary, participants tend to disagree that a damaging earthquake will occur in their community ($M = 2.56, SD = 1.13$) or canton ($M = 2.37, SD = 0.94$).

4.2. EEW system preferences

4.2.1. Knowledge about EEW systems

79.5% of the participants indicated that they know how an EEW system works and 20.5% that they do not. However, by analysing their descriptions of how they think an EEW system works, we identified several misconceptions. First, 14.4% of the participants thought that they will receive the alert some minutes to hours before the earthquake strikes, providing them with plenty of time to take protective actions. Second, 9.4% of the participants thought that an EEW system will predict earthquakes by observing the movements of the earth's plates. Third, 4.2% of the participants believed that changes in seismic activities are detected and the public is warned for upcoming earthquakes. Fourth, 3.4% of the participants thought that foreshocks are registered, and a warning is issued if a strong earthquake is expected to occur. The entire list with the misconceptions is provided in the [Supplement S6](#).

4.2.2. Intensity threshold for warnings

The majority of the participants ([Supplement S7a](#)) would prefer to receive EEW alerts for earthquakes that may be felt (28.2%) or that are certainly felt (30.9%). 26.5% of the participants would prefer to receive a warning only for earthquakes that may cause damage. Only a minority would like to receive alerts for all earthquakes, regardless of whether the shaking could be felt or not (10.6%), or for all earthquake that certainly cause damage (4.0%).

4.2.3. Minimum warning time for an adequate response

44.0% of the participants thought that they need 20 or more seconds between receiving the message and the beginning of the shaking to be able to take protective actions. 23% stated 11–20 s was sufficient warning time, and 21.8% thought 6–10 s was enough. The remaining 11.2% said that 0–5 s would be sufficient ([Supplement S7b](#)).

This is consistent with the participants' answers in QB2, where they were asked whether the time the message had been displayed to them (3 or 5 s; with no significant difference) was enough or not. 60.6% stated that they had not enough time, 25.2% said that they had enough time, and 14.3% were not sure.

Fig. 1. Overview of the first intended reaction people would take when receiving an EEW alert. The bars are divided by colour according to the different measure features that showed a significant effect (see [Table 3](#)). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

4.2.4. Preferred warning channels

When asked about their preferred channels to receive EEW alerts, push notifications on an app ranked first (68%), followed by as many channels as possible (51.5%), public announcements (49.5%), radio messages (39.6%), and TV messages (31.9%); see [Supplement S7c](#). With McNemar tests, we showed that the answer option “push notification via an app” was chosen significantly more often than all the other options ($p < .001$). And the options “as many channels as possible” and “public announcements” were selected significantly more often than radio, TV, social media, other person, computer and specific device ($p < .001$).

4.2.5. Acceptance of technical limitations

We further explored participants’ tolerance for technical limitations of EEW systems. Since no differences in acceptance for technical limitations were observed between the ten EEW message versions, the mean across all versions was calculated (Supplements S8a&b). The participants accepted receiving a second message with more detailed information a few seconds or minutes after the first message had been delivered ($M = 3.78, SD = 1.13$). Likewise, they do not mind if the first message needs to be updated two to three times as new data is becoming available ($M = 3.51, SD = 1.10$). In comparison, they showed a lower tolerance for receiving false alerts ($M = 2.35, SD = 1.22$) or late alerts ($M = 2.31, SD = 1.23$).

4.2.6. Concerns

25.8% of the participants said that they have no concerns regarding the implementation of an EEW system in Switzerland. Those who had concerns mainly thought that they would not have enough time to do anything before the shaking starts (42.1%), most people around them would not take any action (21%), they would not know what to do after having received the message (13.3%), and they do not have to worry because during the last earthquake nothing severe happened (10.2%); see [Supplement S9](#).

4.3. Design of EEW messages

4.3.1. Intended first reactions

Aggregated over all ten EEW message versions, the majority of the participants intend to warn or protect others (23.3%), protect themselves on the spot (21.1%), move near where they deem it safe (16.4%), or run outside (13.6%) as a first reaction after receiving an EEW message ([Fig. 1](#); Supplements S10a-d).

Comparing the ten EEW message versions using a multinomial logistic regression analysis revealed some significant effects with respect to the message attributes ([Table 3](#)).

Compared to participants who received a message with a map, participants who received a message with pictograms are 3.6 times more likely to protect themselves on the spot (e.g., take cover under a table) compared to doing nothing. In comparison, EEW message versions with a map trigger the participants to a higher extent to first warn and protect others.

Compared to participants who received a message for weak shaking, participants who received a message for strong shaking are 5.7

Table 3

Multinomial regression model predicting the intended first reaction depending on the EEW message attributes. The reference level is “do nothing”, thus we looked which EEW message attributes trigger participants to take action compared to taking no actions. Significant effects are highlighted in bold. The absolute number of responses per EEW message attribute is listed in the [Supplement S10d](#).

Message attribute	Protect myself on the spot (cover under a table)				Move nearby where I think it is safe.				
	b	OR	95% CI	Sig.	b	OR	95% CI	Sig.	Sig.
Pictograms	1.29	3.63	[1.53,8.62]	0.003	0.79	2.21	[0.92,5.31]	0.075	
Audio message	1.39	4.00	[1.15,13.94]	0.029	1.23	3.43	[0.96,12.20]	0.058	
Strong shaking	1.73	5.65	[2.28,13.99]	<0.001	1.35	3.87	[1.54,9.75]	0.004	
3 s	-0.4	0.96	[0.42,2.19]	0.916	-0.19	0.83	[0.35,1.93]	0.658	
Message attribute	Stop, and stay still, awaiting the shaking on spot.				Mentally prepare myself for the shaking.				
	b	OR	95% CI	Sig.	b	OR	95% CI	Sig.	Sig.
Pictograms	0.39	1.48	[0.40,5.54]	0.560	-0.04	0.96	[0.33,2.80]	0.940	
Audio message	0.43	1.54	[0.23,10.33]	0.657	1.46	4.29	[1.09,16.80]	0.037	
Strong shaking	0.62	1.86	[0.48,7.23]	0.372	-0.24	0.79	[0.25,2.53]	0.689	
3 s	0.15	1.17	[0.32,4.30]	0.817	0.44	1.55	[0.55,4.39]	0.413	
Message attribute	Run outside.				Look for further information about the earthquake.				
	b	OR	95% CI	Sig.	b	OR	95% CI	Sig.	Sig.
Pictograms	0.46	1.58	[0.65,3.82]	0.311	0.28	1.32	[0.49,3.53]	0.586	
Audio message	0.74	2.09	[0.56,7.82]	0.274	0.89	2.43	[0.60,9.79]	0.211	
Strong shaking	1.44	4.20	[1.64,10.78]	0.003	0.59	1.80	[0.64,5.07]	0.268	
3 s	0.03	1.03	[0.44,2.44]	0.946	0.27	1.31	[0.50,3.45]	0.582	
Message attribute	Report the earthquake.				Warn or protect others.				
	b	OR	95% CI	Sig.	b	OR	95% CI	Sig.	Sig.
Map	2.16	8.64	[0.89,83.75]	0.063	0.29	1.34	[0.58,3.08]	0.494	
Audio message	1.90	6.67	[1.18,37.78]	0.032	0.93	2.55	[0.72,8.95]	0.145	
Strong shaking	0.91	2.48	[0.54,11.27]	0.241	1.28	3.61	[1.47,8.86]	0.005	
3 s	0.69	2.00	[0.32,12.62]	0.461	0.07	1.10	[0.48,2.41]	0.860	

Note: Significant effects are highlighted in bold. CI = confidence interval for OR.

times more likely to protect themselves on the spot (e.g. take cover under a table), 3.9 times more likely to move nearby where they think it is safe, 4.2 times more likely to run outside, and 3.6 times more likely to warn and protect others compared to doing nothing.

Compared to participants who received a visual message, participants who listened to an audio message are 4.0 times more likely to protect themselves on the spot and 4.3 times more likely to mentally prepare themselves for the shaking compared to doing nothing.

There is no significant difference between participants who saw the message only for 3 s and those who saw it for 5 s with regard to taking any action compared to doing nothing.

Regarding the participants' sociodemographic characteristics and earthquake experience, we only had one significant effect. Compared to men, women are 2.8 times more likely to warn or protect others compared to doing nothing ($p = .01$).

4.3.2. Recall of information

Aggregated over the ten EEW message versions, participants on average recalled three out of six information elements correctly ($M = 3.31$, $SD = 1.35$). Participants who saw one of the visual messages (with maps or pictograms) seemed particularly likely to have overlooked that there was an option to report the earthquake. Moreover, the majority of the participants (55%) who saw the weak shaking message with pictograms thought that they have to expect strong shaking even though they only had to expect weak ($F(9,586) = 6.166$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = 0.09$). However, the majority correctly answered that they should not run outside the building during the shaking (Supplements S11a-b).

One-way ANOVAs showed that there are significant differences between the number of correctly answered questions across the different EEW message versions (Supplements S11c-d). First, participants who saw a message with a map were able to recall significantly more information compared to the participants who saw a message with pictograms ($F(1,458) = 28.133$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = 0.06$). Second, participants who listened to an audio message were able to recall significantly more information compared to the participants who saw a visual message ($F(1,594) = 200.124$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = 0.25$). However, this effect has to be interpreted with caution as the audio messages contained less information. Third, participants who saw a message for strong shaking were able to recall significantly more information compared to the participants who saw a message for weak shaking ($F(1,594) = 1.461$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = 0.11$).

4.3.3. Overall rating

The weak shaking message with the pictograms was rated as the version being most understandable, useful, trustworthy, and informative (Fig. 2). Regarding the significant effects, the audio messages for weak and strong shaking were rated as less informative and trustworthy than the weak shaking messages with a map or pictograms (Supplement S12). The message design did not have a significant effect on the perceived comprehension, usefulness and clarity of the message.

We further identified that the age group "18–30 years" significantly rated the messages as less informative ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 1.01$) than the age group "41–50 years" ($M = 4.25$, $SD = 0.91$, $p < .029$) and the age group "61–80 years" ($M = 4.29$, $SD = 0.83$, $p < .027$). In addition, participants who had already experienced an earthquake significantly rated the messages more understandable ($M = 4.32$, $SD = 0.91$) than those who had never experienced an earthquake ($M = 4.16$, $SD = 0.96$, $p < .02$).

Fig. 2. Rating of the EEW message versions, from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. The corresponding statistical tests are in the Supplement S12. The main insight is that all (visual) messages received a very good rating (mean over 4.00).

4.3.4. Evaluation of specific statements

Fig. 3 presents participants' evaluation of specific statements related to the EEW messages. The statement achieving the highest agreement is that the EEW message allows one 'to mentally prepare for the shaking' ($M = 3.90$, $SD = 1.03$). This is followed by they 'would know what to do' ($M = 3.69$, $SD = 1.11$), and 'it is clear whether they are personally affected or not' ($M = 3.67$, $SD = 1.20$). They agreed the least with the statement that they could 'miss the message' ($M = 2.96$, $SD = 1.15$).

Several one-way ANOVAs revealed significant effects of the EEW message attributes on the evaluation of the specific statements (Supplements S13a-b).

Compared to participants who saw a message for strong shaking, for participants who saw a message for weak shaking it was significantly clearer when they have to expect shaking ($F(1,594) = 6.21$, $p = .01$, $\eta^2 = 0.01$). In addition, participants who saw a message for weak shaking indicated to a greater extent that the message would allow them to mentally prepare ($F(1,594) = 7.05$, $p = .008$, $\eta^2 = 0.01$).

Compared to participants who saw a message with pictograms, participants who saw a message with a map knew a little better whether they are personally affected ($F(1,458) = 4.04$, $p = .045$, $\eta^2 = 0.009$). Furthermore, participants who saw one of the visual messages indicated to significantly better know whether they are personally affected compared to those who listened to an audio message ($F(1,594) = 9.93$, $p = .002$, $\eta^2 = 0.02$).

Participants who saw a message for strong shaking were significantly more motivated to take immediate actions ($F(1,594) = 31.43$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = 0.05$). The same applies for participants who saw a message with pictograms ($F(1,458) = 24.80$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = 0.05$) and participants who saw one of the visual messages ($F(1,594) = 3.91$, $p = .049$, $\eta^2 = 0.007$).

Compared to participants who listened to an audio message, participants who saw a visual message indicated to significantly better know what they should do ($F(1,594) = 60.34$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = 0.09$).

5. Discussion

With this study, we explored the interest and the preferences of the public towards EEW in a country with moderate seismic hazard. The results clearly show that the Swiss public would like to receive EEW alerts with similar interest as it has been observed in New Zealand [14] and countries such as Japan, Mexico, or the US, where EEW alerts are already publicly available. Even though many of the general preferences of the Swiss public are in line with those observed in other countries, some differ as discussed in section 5.1. The results further show that the ten EEW message versions tested trigger different actions and that the preferred message designs not necessarily support people best in taking appropriate actions (section 5.2). Even though all visual EEW messages were well perceived, the content of some messages was better recalled than of others (section 5.2). Our findings thus shed light on the preferences with regards to an EEW system in regions with moderate seismic hazard. In addition, they provide valuable insights with respect to the design of EEW messages (section 5.3).

5.1. Preferred attributes of EEW systems

We assessed public's preferred warning thresholds and warning times, how they would like to receive the warnings, and which concerns they have regarding EEW systems. Fig. 4 summarizes the main results.

Regarding the **warning threshold** to receive EEW messages, the majority in Switzerland prefer to receive EEW alerts for all earthquakes that may be or are certainly felt (beginning from MMI III-IV), which is in line with the recommendations given by Bossu

Fig. 3. Evaluation of specific statements related to the EEW messages, from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree and aggregated over the ten EEW message versions.

Fig. 4. Overview of the main insights regarding the attributes of and issues with an EEW system.

et al. [34]. In practice for the US ShakeAlert system, the alert thresholds range from MMI III to V, depending on the means of delivery [71]. This differs from the preferences found in New Zealand, where the preferred minimum threshold is set slightly higher at MMI V-VI [36], and in Japan, where warnings are only sent for events with intensities of MMI VI-VII or above [35]. This may be explained by the fact that in these countries, the population have experience of earthquakes with higher intensities and, thus, only want to be alerted for earthquakes that can be widely felt and cause damages. Thus, alert thresholds should be flexible and adjusted to people's preferences.

Regarding the **warning time**, compared to New Zealand where the majority of the participants stated that 5–10 s will be sufficient to take simple protective actions [14], the majority of the participants in Switzerland would like to have more than 10 s, despite the fact such a long alert time can only very rarely be provided [72]. However, Emolo et al. [53] showed that, for trained people, 3–5 s are enough to take preventative action, which is line with the experiences in other countries with operational EEW systems. Further, our results showed that the information can be correctly understood within 3–5 s, thus combined with a good training, effective responses in a few seconds are possible. In Switzerland, training campaigns would be needed so that people know exactly what they should do in specific situations [10,19], transforming declarative knowledge into procedural knowledge [52] and, consequently, reducing people's response time.

Regarding **dissemination channels**, the Swiss public prefers to receive the EEW alerts as push notifications on their mobile phones supported by other channels (mainly public sirens and radio), which is in line with the preferences in New Zealand [14] and Mexico [29]. The 'MyShake' app in California (US) for example shows that dedicated EEW apps can achieve high penetration rates at least in high hazard regions. In comparison, in countries where felt and damaging earthquakes only occur rarely, it may be more effective to disseminate the warnings via already existing and widely used apps, such as national weather apps [27,63]. Alternatively or in addition, cell broadcasting can be used to warn everyone, including tourists, in the affected areas regardless of whether they have downloaded an app or not [10]. However, the legal frameworks for the use of cell broadcasting are not available in all European countries, including Switzerland, and an ongoing challenge with the technology is to provide low latency alerts to all target recipients. In addition, privately operated systems, such as Google [22], also started sending EEW notifications to their users. Since most participants in the current and in other studies wished to be informed via as many channels as possible, a multi-channel distribution not only meets the user needs but also enhances the resilience of the distribution. However, inconsistent messages among the channels can lead to confusion and, consequently, inaction, as Weyrich et al. [73] showed for weather warnings. Thus, it is recommended that the different providers of the messages should report the same information preferably from an official authoritative source.

The Swiss people who had **concerns** worried most not having enough time to react, being around people who would not take actions, or not knowing what to do when receiving an EEW alert. Thus, in parallel to the technical considerations, resources also have to be invested in education and outreach efforts [19]. In addition, the normalization bias has to be addressed by keeping the communication efforts on-going when an EEW system is operational [14]. And lastly, people's perceived self-efficacy is key to ensure that they take action [74].

The **technical limitations** such as short or late warning times for the areas receiving the strongest shaking [6–8] or the possibility of false alerts [10] have to be transparently communicated to the public [35,61]. In comparison to the people in Mexico and Japan [29, 55], the Swiss public shows a low acceptance for false and late alerts. This may be explained by the fact that people in Mexico and

Japan have a higher risk perception and experience strong earthquake more frequently and, thus, perceive false alerts as an opportunity to practice the behavioral responses. However for weather-related events, Johnson et al. [57] showed that too many false alerts can negatively affect the credibility of the system. In Switzerland it will be expected that a first alert should be followed by a message with more detailed information sent some minutes after the event. This second message might also counteract mistrust in the system after a false alert [35] and also warn about secondary hazards such as fires, landslides or tsunamis [14].

Although people tend to think they know how an EEW system works, we identified several **misconceptions**. People believe that they have plenty of time between receiving the warning and the beginning of the shaking, that EEW systems predict earthquakes, or that foreshocks have been observed and function a warning for an upcoming bigger event. These misconceptions have to be addressed by providing explanatory material and high quality and persistent educational training. Sutton et al. [52] for example showed that instructional videos can increase people's understanding of EEW systems and their technical limitations.

5.2. The impact of the design of EEW messages

In total, ten different EEW message versions were tested in this study. Fig. 5 summarizes the elements which would have triggered action taking; are perceived as most useful, trustworthy, understandable, and clear; and allow people to recall most information. Our experimental design allowed us to put the participants in a stressful situation because they only had either 3 or 5 s to look at the EEW message.

Previous studies emphasized that different message elements can trigger different actions. Wood [39] claimed that the information provided should be actionable and allow people to take fast decisions. Kreuzmair et al. [40] concluded that pictograms increase public's compliance to warning information. Our study confirms this finding, pictograms enhanced the intention to take protective actions on the spot. Pictograms also help people who do not understand the written text in knowing what to do. Including maps in the message triggers people to warn and protect others and to access further information. The impulses to first look for further information or to protect others before taking actions are confirmed by Nakayachi et al. [13] and Fallou et al. [26] respectively. However, people do not have enough time to look for further information when receiving an EEW alert, they immediately need to take protective actions. The advantage of the map is that participants knew that they are affected. However, with information campaigns, people can be informed that when they receive such an alert they are always affected. We thus recommend that pictograms are used for EEW alerts, triggering people to protect themselves. Maps should be rather used for subsequent messages since they motivate people to look for further information. However, our results also reveal that people prefer messages with maps over those with pictograms (Supplement S14). Thus, the most preferred message type does not necessarily encourage people to take the most appropriate protective action.

Even though the audio messages were rated as less trustworthy and useful, they successfully triggered participants intentions to take actions or to mentally prepare. And if a person is in a separate room than their mobile phone, they could still hear the alert and take action. Audio messages also have an added value for people with low reading skills or impaired sight. Thus, combined with written information, an audio message might be an added value, which should be tested in future studies.

Regarding the placing of the information, we showed that the highlighted title and the information in the middle (map or pictograms) was better recalled than the information (report an earthquake button/more information) at the bottom of the warning. This is a positive finding because people can use the highlighted information to take action and the less visible information can be read after

Fig. 5. Overview of the main insights regarding the EEW messages.

the shaking. Thus, with the thoughtful arrangement of the information and the appropriate use of colours, one can ensure that people get the relevant information in the few seconds they have to react.

Moreover, the intensity level influences the intention to take actions or not. People who receive a warning for strong shaking have stronger intentions to take protective actions compared to those who receive a warning for weak shaking and more often intend to do nothing. This implies that people respond proportionally to their risk exposure. Moreover, the information of the strong shaking warnings is better recalled. One reason could be that people recognize the severity of the event and, consequently then pay more attention. Potentially, this is supported by the design for strong shaking, which is dominated by a red header banner. In comparison, weak shaking warnings motivate people to look for further information. The fact that they want to access further information provides an opportunity to inform them in more detail about earthquakes and what preventative actions they should take. Thus, weak shaking messages are key in the information service, functioning as an awareness tool.

Last, there are no significant differences in perception or behavioral intentions between the 3 and 5 s message display. They represent typical warning times to be expected for an operational EEW system in Switzerland (environmental validity). In countries where longer warning times are more likely, the between-subject experiment could also be conducted with for example 10 or 15 s.

5.3. Limitations and practical implications

In this survey, the participants were only introduced to a hypothetical scenario, and we do not know whether they would take the actions they indicated in a real-world situation. However, the limited time display imitated a stressful situation, similar to when a real warning is received. This allowed us to identify the amount of information that can be recalled in a short time and also to determine how the message is perceived. The robustness of our results is further substantiated by the fact that they are in line with studies in countries where EEW systems are already operational. They thus offer a good data base for future cross-cultural comparisons. In addition, since to our knowledge this study is the first to test and compare different EEW message designs, it also provides valuable information to improve EEW messages elsewhere.

Even though it is the first public survey conducted in a country with moderate seismic hazard, Switzerland is a rich country with strong adherence to a good building code. Thus, comparisons with countries with a higher vulnerability may reveal differences regarding system preferences and protective actions people would take. We thus collaborate with a research group which is assessing public perception of EEW systems in Central America [75] to provide further cross-cultural comparisons.

Besides the socio-demographic and normative factors we considered in our study, the influence of other factors such as fear, uncertainty, shock-induced paralysis, or self-efficacy on people's intention to react to an EEW alert should be assessed [74,76]. Such additional insights would help to develop information campaigns and training for communities with specific needs. Further research is also needed to better understand the needs of vulnerable groups to receive and to act on EEW since they are most affected by disasters [77,78]. Jenkins et al. [62] developed a framework based on self-reflective questions to ensure that vulnerable groups are better targeted in the outreach activities of EEW systems, consequently making communication practices more inclusive.

Due to the current proliferation of cell-phones at all levels of society, apps are currently at the forefront of EEW alert dissemination. However, communication infrastructure is constantly evolving and new actors and channels for disseminating EEW alerts may enter the field, for example operated by specific initiatives or streaming services [22,79]. To avoid inconsistent messages, providers of EEW alerts should coordinate their efforts and join forces to reach large parts of society.

Current cost-benefit analyses [80] would benefit from integrating insights from public surveys, to either confirm the effectiveness of already operating EEW systems or to proof the potential of EEW systems in the testing phase. Together with the EEW experts at the Swiss Seismological Service at ETH Zurich we thus integrated data related to people's intention to take action and false alert tolerance into the cost-benefit analysis of the Swiss EEW system; see Refs. [72,81].

6. Conclusions

This study offers insights into what people in a country with a moderate seismic hazard expect from an EEW system. Further, the study quantifies for the first time the impact different EEW message designs have on public perception and behavioral intentions, providing relevant guidelines for disaster managers, communication experts or institutions charged with designing effective and user-centred EEW alerts. The findings show that well-designed warnings increase people's intention to react in time and to take appropriate measures. When EEW messages include pictograms, people have stronger intentions to take protective actions on the spot whereas maps motivate people to look for further information or inform others about what happened. However, if the respondents are allowed to make their own decision on which design they like best, the majority opts for the message with a map. Hence, what people like best is not necessarily what helps them most. In consequence, the message elements that support people best in taking relevant decisions needs to be assessed, and a design that adjusts to the expected level of shaking the user will experience might be beneficial for optimal user action. This requires quantitative and qualitative experiments in hypothetical and real-world settings. Furthermore, the design of an EEW systems should follow a transdisciplinary approach to ensure the collaboration between scientists from different disciplines and stakeholders of the society including the public. Only then can technical and societal issues be jointly and sufficiently addressed, allowing user-oriented services to emerge that take full advantage of an EEW system.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Dr Sarah Dryhurst, Dr Alexandra Freeman and Giulia Luoni (Winton Centre for Risk & Evidence Communication, University of Cambridge) and Nadja Valenzuela (Swiss Seismological Service at ETH Zurich) for their feedback on the survey design and all participants for taking part in the survey. The authors also thank the reviewers for their valuable comments, which improved the clarity of our article.

This project is part of the Real-time Earthquake Risk Reduction for a Resilient Europe 'RISE' project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 821115. Opinions expressed in this paper solely reflect the authors' view; the EU is not responsible for any use that may be made of information it contains. This research was approved by the Ethics Committee of ETH Zurich (EK 2020-N-46).

Specific contributions of the authors: ID & MM: conceptualized the study and wrote the article; ID: launched the survey, did the analysis and created the figures; JC, MB & FM: provided feedback on the survey, including the scientific correctness of the technical details of EEW alerts; helped with writing the article; FM: translated the survey into French; and SZ: designed the mock-up alert messages for the survey.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2022.103441>.

Appendix B. Overview of the survey questions

The values are aggregated over all participants. The detail statistics are available in the supplementary material (Appendix A). For the questions where we indicate the mean and standard deviation (SD), we used a 5-point Likert scale.

Items	%	Mean	SD	Reference [adapted from]
QB1 Please indicate any previous experience you have had with earthquakes.				(Becker et al., 2020)
<i>I have personally felt an earthquake before.</i>	63.1			
<i>I have experienced personal injury, damage or loss from an earthquake.</i>	1.9			
<i>I have had family or friends injured, or experienced damage or loss from an earthquake.</i>	7.4			
<i>I have observed local earthquake damage or loss (e.g., in my neighbourhood or city)</i>	10.6			
<i>I have learned about earthquake damage at school.</i>	37.1			
<i>I have observed earthquake damage or loss via the media (e.g., documentary or on television or news articles in the internet).</i>	71.5			
<i>I have seen earthquake effects in movies or series.</i>	64.3			
<i>None of the above answers.</i>	3.4			
How strong was the strongest earthquake shaking that you ever felt?				
<i>Weak shaking (felt, but first unsure if it was a quake)</i>	33.4			
<i>Mild shaking (dishes, windows, doors shake)</i>	44.7			
<i>Moderate shaking (Hanging object swing considerably, small objects are shifted)</i>	15.5			
<i>Strong shaking (Some objects fall, slight non-structural damage like cracks on the wall)</i>	4.5			
<i>Very strong shaking (Furniture is shifted, objects fall from shelves, large cracks in walls)</i>	1.8			
What was your first response while or after the earthquake was shaking?				
<i>I woke up.</i>	23.2			
<i>I woke up and immediately felt asleep again.</i>	18.3			
<i>I stopped what I was doing but stayed still.</i>	45.8			
<i>I went under a table or doorframe.</i>	6.8			
<i>I ran outside.</i>	6.0			
<i>I tried to protect other people, pets or property nearby.</i>	4.9			
<i>I slowed down and pulled over to the side of the road.</i>	1.9			
<i>I looked for information on the internet.</i>	24.8			
<i>I talked to friends, my family or neighbours.</i>	38.4			
<i>Other: [text]</i>	-			
How did you feel during or after the shaking?				
<i>I was very scared.</i>		2.12	1.20	
<i>I felt helpless.</i>		2.60	1.37	
<i>I was worried about my family and friends.</i>		2.33	1.31	
<i>I found it exciting.</i>		2.85	1.32	
<i>I was not worried at all.</i>		3.19	1.38	
<i>Other: [textbox]</i>		-	-	

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Items	%	Mean	SD	Reference [adapted from]
The following things can be done to prepare for an earthquake. Which of these have you or your household done, before today?				(Becker et al., 2020)
<i>I have informed myself on how to prepare for an emergency such as earthquakes.</i>	40.3			
<i>I have prepared essential items specifically for an emergency (e.g., food, water, first aid kit, medicines, emergency get away kit).</i>	19.7			
<i>I took measures to increase my residence's earthquake resistance (e.g., secured furniture, built earthquake resistant).</i>	5.4			
<i>I have prepared a family emergency plan.</i>	7.4			
<i>I have informed myself on how to respond to strong earthquake shaking.</i>	66.6			
<i>I have practiced responding to an earthquake drill (on my own or as part of a drill).</i>	15.4			
<i>I have responded to real earthquake shaking by taking protective action and thus know what to do during strong shaking.</i>	9.4			
<i>I have sufficient home insurance cover that will allow me to rebuild should my home be severely damaged.</i>	13.7			
<i>Other: [text]</i>	-			
<i>None of the above measures.</i>	42.1			
To what extent do you agree with the following statements:				
<i>A damaging earthquake will occur in my community in my lifetime.</i>		2.56	1.13	
<i>A damaging earthquake might happen in my canton, but it won't happen near me.</i>		2.37	0.94	
<i>A damaging earthquake in Switzerland is possible.</i>		3.30	1.13	
<i>A damaging earthquake in Switzerland is probable.</i>		2.79	1.10	
<i>A damaging earthquake would impact my life.</i>		3.41	1.11	
Do you know how an earthquake early warning system works?				(Becker et al., 2020)
<i>Yes</i>	79.5			
<i>No</i>	20.5			
Please describe in two to three sentences what you understand under an earthquake early warning system:				
<i>[Open-answer question]</i>				
QB2 What would you do first after receiving this message?				(Becker et al., 2020)
<i>Do nothing/undertake no actions.</i>	5.5			
<i>Protect myself on the spot (e.g., take cover under a table).</i>	21.1			
<i>Move nearby to where I think it is safe.</i>	16.4			
<i>Stop, and stay still, awaiting the shaking on spot.</i>	2.5			
<i>Mentally prepare myself for the shaking.</i>	6.7			
<i>Run outside.</i>	13.6			
<i>Look for further information about the earthquake.</i>	7.7			
<i>Report the earthquake.</i>	1.7			
<i>Warn or protect others.</i>	23.2			
<i>Others</i>	1.6			
Please remember the message you have just received. Tick all the statements that correspond to what you have just seen or heard.				
<i>There was the possibility to report the earthquake.</i>	30.7			
<i>There was the possibility to access more information.</i>	39.4			
<i>Weak shaking was expected at my location in the city of Fribourg.</i>	67.8			
<i>It was recommended to take cover under a table.</i>	61.9			
<i>It was recommended to do nothing.</i>	49.2			
<i>It was recommended to run out of the building.</i>	81.7			
Did you have enough time to gather all the information that was important to you?				
<i>Yes</i>	25.2			
<i>No</i>	60.6			
<i>I don't know</i>	14.3			
What would be the minimum warning time you think you would need to respond (i.e., between receiving the warning and feeling the shaking)?				(Becker et al., 2020)
<i>0-2 s or at the same time as the warning</i>	2.0			
<i>3-5 s</i>	9.2			
<i>6-10 s</i>	21.8			
<i>11-20 s</i>	23.0			
<i>20 s or more</i>	44.0			
QB3 Please rate how you perceived the message.				
<i>Useful</i>		4.21	0.95	
<i>Trustworthy</i>		4.15	0.94	
<i>Understandable</i>		4.26	0.93	
<i>Clear</i>		4.13	0.97	
<i>Informative</i>		4.12	0.96	
With regard to the message above, how much do you agree with the following statements?				(Becker et al., 2020)
<i>I would know what to do.</i>		3.69	1.11	
<i>It is clear to me when I have to expect shaking.</i>		3.26	1.27	

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(continued)

Items	%	Mean	SD	Reference [adapted from]
It is clear to me whether I personally would be affected in the city of Fribourg or not.		3.47	1.17	
The message motivates me to take immediate actions (e.g., take cover under a table).		3.67	1.20	
The message motivates me to look for more information about earthquakes (e.g., what happened, how can I prepare).		3.26	1.19	
The message allows me to mentally prepare myself for the shaking.		3.90	1.03	
I would surely miss the message (e.g., not see or hear the message) and therefore it would not be useful for me.		2.96	1.15	
Please indicate which is the minimum level of shaking you think would be useful to be warned for.				(Becker et al., 2020)
For all earthquakes, independent of whether the shaking could be felt or not.	10.6			
For all earthquakes that I may will feel.	28.2			
For all earthquakes that I certainly will feel.	30.9			
For all earthquakes that may cause damage.	26.3			
For all earthquakes that certainly cause damage.	4.0			
Would you also want to receive earthquake early warnings under the following circumstances?				
You receive five to ten false alerts per year.		2.35	1.22	
You frequently receive warnings of earthquakes that are not as strong as indicated in the message.		2.63	1.18	
You frequently receive warnings of possible shaking at your location, but you do not feel shaking afterwards.		2.41	1.17	
You receive most of the messages after you have already felt the shaking.		2.31	1.23	
You receive a second message a few seconds to minutes after the first message with more detailed information about the earthquake.		3.78	1.13	
The information of the first message (e.g., magnitude) has to be updated two to three times in the first minutes after the shaking due to new available data.		3.52	1.08	
Assuming that you have the possibility to receive such earthquake early warnings. What would be your greatest concerns regarding possible actions?				
I would not know what to do after having received the message.	13.3			
I am not sure whether I would understand the warning.	7.4			
Nothing happened to me during past earthquakes, so I think I do not need earthquake early warnings.	10.2			
I think it does not matter what I would do as it would be useless anyway.	7.9			
I think most people around me would not do anything too if they received such a warning.	21.0			
I would not have enough time to do anything before it starts shaking.	42.1			
I would panic and thus would not be able to do anything.	8.6			
None of the above answers.	25.8			
How would you prefer to receive an earthquake early warning?				(Becker et al., 2020)
Push notification via an app on the smartphone	68.0			
Personal computer (with software that can receive the EEW alert)	10.1			
TV message (e.g., Banner)	31.9			
Radio message	39.6			
Public announcement (e.g., via loudspeaker or siren)	49.5			
Another person (e.g., family member, friend, neighbour, workmate)	11.7			
Using a specific device designed to receive an EEW alert (e.g., a device used in the home or workplace)	7.2			
Social media (e.g., Tweet on Twitter)	16.6			
Through as many channels as possible at the same time	51.5			
Other: [textline]				
Imagine you could subscribe to earthquake early warning push notification. Thereby, you can choose by yourself for which events you will be informed. In some cases, you will receive the message before you feel the shaking and in other a few seconds after. Which message format would you prefer under these circumstances?				
Version with the map	75.0			
Version with pictograms	25.0			
Question block 4 is not listed here because not relevant for this article [the questions are listed in the Supplement S3c if of interest]				
QB5 Sociodemographic characteristics [Supplements S1a-d]				
- Gender				
- Age				
- Living place				
- Highest educational degree				
- Work				
- Household age groups				
- Persons with disabilities				
- Earthquake insurance				
- Building type				
- Income				

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